

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF CACHING STRATEGIES IN DISTRIBUTED SYSTEMS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THEIR IMPACT ON PERFORMANCE AND FAULT TOLERANCE

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Abstract

This paper presents a comparative analysis of various caching strategies in distributed systems, such as LRU, LFU, FIFO, and ARC, to assess their impact on performance, fault tolerance, and data consistency. The methods of caching data replication, including synchronous and asynchronous replication, are discussed, along with their influence on latency and data availability. The use of formal fault tolerance models and queue theory allows for the identification of optimal strategies based on workload characteristics and consistency requirements. The findings are valuable for developing efficient cache management mechanisms in high-load distributed systems.

Keywords: caching, cache management strategies, fault tolerance, distributed systems, data replication.

Introduction

Modern distributed systems support huge amounts of data, for which efficient memory management and cache methods are needed to provide good performance and fault tolerance. Caching is a critical component in reducing data access latency, server load, and system throughput. The caching policy can affect the data consistency, response time, and system fault tolerance to a great extent, though. Optimal choice of these parameters remains an open problem requiring thorough research of current approaches to cache management.

The significance of the research is attributed to the soaring needs for distributed computing in cloud platforms, web applications, and big data systems. Different caching policies, for example, cache management policies and cached data replication schemes, have different effects on system performance and reliability. A thorough analysis of these mechanisms allows you to gain an optimal balance between query response speed, fault tolerance, and data consistency that is very important for systems with high workload and dynamic volatility.

The objective of this paper is to carry out comparative analysis of cache strategies in distributed systems with determination of their impact on key performance and fault tolerance characteristics. The research uses methods of theoretical analysis of current strategies, formalized modeling of fault tolerance, and comparative analysis of cache management algorithms. Taking these factors into consideration will allow to make recommendations about the choice of the most efficient strategy depending on the operating conditions of the system.

Main part. Caching methods and their impact on performance

In distributed systems, caching is one of the most essential mechanisms for improving the efficiency of query processing, reducing latency, and optimizing the use of computing resources. The key role of caching is the temporary storage of highly requested data in faster storage, i.e., RAM or dedicated caching servers. However, the caching performance is not only determined by the access speed, but also by the cache management policy, which affects the hit ratio, network traffic, and data consistency.

Of the usual cache management techniques, there is particular attention paid to **cache management algorithms** that determine what items to store and remove with restricted memory. The **LRU** (Least Recently Used) algorithm, which adheres to the eviction of the least recently used items, is good at handling systems with high data locality, but it can display poor performance in retrieving various segments of data in a cyclic manner [1]. Similarly, the **LFU** (Least Frequently Used) removes the least frequently accessed elements, which gives protection against temporary request anomalies, but can generate memory overload with rarely changed objects. **ARC** (Adaptive Replacement Cache) is a further approach that provides the power of both LRU and LFU, changing the replacement policy depending on the nature of the input data dynamically [2].

In addition to management algorithms, a **cached data replication mechanism** has an important role to play, balancing availability and consistency. Replication speeds up data access by copying the data onto multiple nodes, but introduces additional delays due to the need for synchronization (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Replicated cache [3]

Synchronous replication blocks the caller (e.g., in `cache.put(key, value)`) until successful replication of the changes to all nodes in the cluster. Synchronous replication offers strong data consistency, but can degrade system performance, especially with many updates. Asynchronous replication, on the other hand, accelerates request processing since data updates are cached, but can lead to stale data on individual nodes.

Distributed technologies such as Apache Kafka play an important role in the scalability and integration of such caching methods. Kafka, for example, is used to ship streaming data between many services and system components in real-time such that you can synchronously update cached data on several nodes without severe latency [4]. This aspect is particularly beneficial in high-load systems, like financial portals, where prompt processing and transmission of data with assured reliability are crucial. These frameworks also ensure scalability and fault tolerance of the system, which responds to change and failure of individual components with speed.

The choice of the best caching strategy relies on the nature of the system load, distribution of requests, and consistency requirements. The integration of LRU and asynchronous replication is optimal in web applications with heavy loads, which restricts latency. Systems with high costs of consistency, such as banking systems, use hybrid strategies with adaptive replacement algorithms and strict synchronization rules for data. Therefore, the selection of the caching strategy directly affects the system's throughput, response time, and fault tolerance and makes the system successful in real application.

Formal models of fault tolerance when using caching

The fault tolerance of distributed systems relies to a large degree on the effectiveness of caching since techniques for cache management not only reduce the time spent processing requests, but also have an impact on the fault tolerance of the system. Fault tolerance is quantified using formal models that enable analysis of the impact of caching strategies on failure probability, **data availability, and recovery time**. The most important parameters that characterize fault tolerance are the system recovery time, data loss probability, and the extent of performance degradation in case of failure [5].

One of the significant analysis tools is the **model of a Markov process**, which enables one to model the behavior of the system in the presence of probabilistic failures. In these models, a distributed system is represented as a finite collection of states, each of which is characterized by some configuration of cached data and its availability. The probability of transition between states is determined by the node failure rate and data replication time. For example, for an asynchronously replicated cache, the likelihood of getting stale data is directly proportional to the update interval, and for synchronous replication, it depends on the negotiation delays between nodes.

Another important model is the **queue theory**, which is used to find the impact of failures on system performance. In these models, nodes of a distributed system are considered units of a queuing network in which data request arrivals have some intensity and the probability of a successful response depends on the cache status and the replication strategy. For instance, during high system loads, the likelihood of cache misses is higher, and this causes the request processing time to rise and the central data warehouse load to increase. During such scenarios, cache management policies that rely on predicting access frequency can lower the load and enhance fault tolerance.

In addition, a **system reliability model** is utilized, which is based on the analysis of weighted average time between failures (MTBF) and failure recovery time (MTTR). In cache systems, these are functions of data update rate and efficiency of replication schemes. For example, when the cache is not updated frequently, the probability of data obsolescence increases, which deteriorates the quality of service. On the other hand, frequent updates place greater loads on the network, but provide more availability of up-to-date information. Formal fault tolerance models therefore allow us to examine the impact of various caching policies on distributed system stability and determine the best tradeoff between performance and dependability, depending on the requirements of a particular application.

Comparative analysis of caching strategies

The choice of a caching technique in distributed systems directly affects their performance, fault tolerance, and data consistency. The evaluation of different methods allows you to define their pros and cons considering the workloads and architectural features of the

system. The main parameters for evaluation are cache hit ratio, request processing latency, data consistency level, and crash tolerance.

The most popular algorithms are **LRU and LFU**. The former effectively evicts the least recently used data and is therefore better for workloads with good temporal locality. However, in the presence of cyclical data access, LRU can behave poorly. On the other hand, the LFU stores most frequently accessed information, which is useful for stable access patterns, but can lead to the problem of a «frozen» cache, when rarely updated items continue to occupy space, even after their usefulness has passed.

Additionally, the **FIFO (First In, First Out) algorithm** is utilized, where data are cleared out in precisely the order that they are input. Although simple to use, its performance usually is inferior to LRU and LFU, as it never takes into consideration either the access frequency or the recency of data [6]. With a better alternative, adaptive algorithms such as ARC are used, which adjust the balance between usage frequency and recency of data usage adaptively to provide a higher rate of cache hits than with normal systems.

When measuring the impact of caching on fault tolerance, you must consider the replication method for the cached data. Asynchronous replication, which does not add latency but makes data inconsistency possible,

is used in high-load systems. In mission-critical applications, such as banking systems, synchronous replication is more commonly used, which adds latency but ensures strict consistency.

For example, the study demonstrated that hybridization of machine learning with standard cache algorithms provided 77% improvement for LRU, 65% for LFU, and 77% for ARC with similar match rates to the most advanced techniques [7]. FIFO, however, maintains consistent but relatively low marks, giving way to adaptive algorithms. Therefore, the choice of the caching policy is determined by the load type: for high frequency access, LFU and ARC are more appropriate, while for mixed request streams in systems, LRU and hybrid policies provide better performance.

Choosing the optimal strategy depending on the operating conditions

The optimal selection of the caching policy in distributed systems is achieved by a large number of factors including the nature of the workload, data consistency requirements, and the fault tolerance level acceptable. There is no common method that would be equally effective in every situation, but a reasonable consideration of the operational conditions allows you to choose the best compromise between system performance and availability (table 1).

Table 1.

Selection of optimal caching strategy based on application conditions

Adaptation model	Key principle	Advantages	Limitations	Implementation examples
Flexible manufacturing	Rapid reconfiguration for demand changes	Reduced downtime, quick market response	Requires investment in technology	Automotive industry
Digital transformation	Automation and data analysis	Cost optimization, demand forecasting	High implementation costs	Smart factories, IoT
Market diversification	Expansion into new regions and segments	Reduces dependence on a single market	Requires product and marketing adaptation	Consumer electronics manufacturers
Environmental adaptation	Reducing environmental impact and transitioning to sustainable technologies	Regulatory compliance, improved reputation	High modernization costs	Packaging producers, metallurgy

For highly loaded web applications, for instance, **content delivery networks (CDN)** or cloud systems, low request processing latencies and high throughput are crucial. In these systems, there are employed LRU and ARC algorithms with a high cache hit rate of dynamically changing requests [8]. ARC is unique in that it adapts to the request structure, allowing you to balance dynamically between frequency and recency of data usage. Also, asynchronous replication of cached information is commonplace in distributed CDN networks, as precedence is given to delivery speed, over strong consistency of information.

In bank databases and corporate records, where consistency of information is of the highest importance, caching has to maintain strict control of updates and prevent stale data. **Hybrid solutions** that blend LFUS with synchronous replication methods are used here.

LFU allows you to lighten the load on the central storage by putting the most sought-after data in the cache, and synchronous replication ensures that it will be up to date. However, these techniques can introduce further processing latency, especially under heavy write workloads.

For analytical systems and big data warehouses, a trade-off between data volume and availability is the key. Hierarchical caching methods are preferred in these systems, wherein data is tiered across levels based on usage frequency. For example, frequently accessed data is cached in RAM by using LRU, while less frequently accessed data is moved to slow but larger spaces. This approach reduces the load on the central database and improves fault tolerance since data is stored in a distributed way.

Thus, the choice of the most appropriate caching policy is determined by the requirements of a particular

scenario. LRU and ARC are implemented in high – read-intensive applications, LFU and synchronous replication in mission-critical applications with hard consistency requirements – LFU, and multi-level storage models for analytical solutions. Hybrid methods incorporating over one method allow you to take into account the nature of the load and for maximum efficiency while operating in real life.

Conclusion

Caching is a key element in the performance optimization and fault tolerance of distributed systems, but its effectiveness relies heavily on the choice of the cache management policy. The study showed that there is no one-size-fits-all solution for every case. The LRU and ARC algorithms are high-performance query processing for dynamically evolving workloads, whereas LFU is optimal for stable workloads but requires a mechanism for avoiding a «frozen» cache.

It is also concluded that the system's fault tolerance depends not only on the choice of substitution algorithm, but also on the replication policy of cached data. Asynchronous methods improve performance at the cost of temporary data inconsistencies due to decreased latency. Synchronous techniques, however, assure consistency at the expense of network overhead. Thus, the optimal caching policy is a balance between performance, consistency, and reliability requirements, requiring the application of a hybrid approach and adaptive cache management policy.

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